

Temperature Dependent Schrodinger Equation and A Particle in a Box

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Recently, there have been a number of articles in the literature describing Schrodinger type equations modified to account for temperature. In general, these are of the form of the regular Schrodinger equation with an extra potential term dependent on temperature and the wavefunction. It should be noted that temperature dependent Hartree Fock theory for a nucleus includes temperature induced changes to the potential felt by a single particle and so the single particle levels calculated are modified by temperature. Temperature dependent Hartree Fock, however, is not the same as the new Schrodinger type equations presented in the literature. In this note, we consider the case of a single particle in a box and consider $dU=TdS$, where U is the energy, T the temperature and S Shannon's entropy in momentum space. We obtain a value for f_p , the momentum distribution, by varying f_p and use a Fourier transform to find the wavefunction. We then compare the result to predictions of equations in the literature.

Traditional Approach to a Particle in a Box

Traditionally, a particle in a box with a temperature T is handled in the following manner, it seems. First, single particle states are obtained without any consideration of temperature, namely $\sin(kx)$ with $k=6.28 n/L$ where L is the length of the box and n an integer. This ensures the wavefunction disappears at $x=0$ and $x=L$. Next, it is assumed the particle must be in one of these states and maximization of entropy leads to a weight of $\exp(-p^2/2mT)$ for each in the same manner used in classical statistical mechanics. There is no interference so density is given by:

$$\text{density}(x) = \sum_{n=1,2,3..} C \exp(-p_n^2/2mT) \sin(p_n x) \sin(p_n x) \quad ((1))$$

Where $p_n = 6.28 n/L$

New Suggested Approach

It seems that new approaches in the literature (1),(2) are suggesting that temperature can actually change the form of the wavefunction, unlike the picture presented in ((1)). Temperature dependent Hartree Fock theory already makes this assumption to obtain temperature modified single particle energy levels, but then basically follows the non-interference picture of ((1)).

Consider a plane wave $\exp(ikx)$ in a box. It will reflect to produce $\exp(-ikx)$ and the two will interfere. At the same time, only results with $k=6.28n/L$ will produce resonances. It is suggested that there is an internal zitterbewegung cycle responsible for this, although mathematically one

states that the wavefunction must vanish at $x=0$ and $x=L$. If temperature is present in the system, this seems to suggest that some kind of interactions are occurring with the plane waves. In classical statistical mechanics, temperature is manifested by photons or collisions, for example. Thus, instead of having $\exp(ik_1 x)$ and $\exp(-ik_1 x)$, these two waves may interact and other waves such as $\exp(ik_2 x)$ and $\exp(-ik_2 x)$ be produced. Thus, one might suggest a new wavefunction of the form:

$W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$ where $p = 6.28 n/L$ so the wavefunction vanishes at the boundary.

This is exactly the type of solution used for a particle in a potential. Instead of the particle forming a resonance with the potential $V(x)$, it is forming one through interactions with the "particles" supplying the temperature.

Next, consider the idea of entropy. Shannon's entropy is given by $-k \sum P_i \ln(P_i)$ where P_i is the probability of the i th state. For the case of a particle in a box, one can calculate spatial entropy density or momentum entropy. Spatial entropy density, used in (2) is given by:

$$S \text{ density} = -k \int W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)] \quad ((2))$$

Here $W(x) = \sin(kx)$ with $k=6.28 n/L$. Thus, for each n , one obtains a different spatial entropy density.

Momentum entropy seems to be different. We write it as others do in the literature as:

$$S \text{ momentum} = -k \sum_p f_p \ln[f_p] \quad ((3))$$

It is of the same form as ((2)), but seems to be different as the weights of the $\exp(ikx)$ are always $1/2$ (or $1/2i$) regardless of n in $k=6.28 n/L$ for a state $\sin(kx)$.

Next, we follow (1) and (2) in writing, from thermodynamics with $dW_{\text{work}}=0$:

$$dU = TdS \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } U \text{ is internal energy and } T \text{ temperature}$$

We, however, suggest that dU and dS are obtained by changing F_p to $F_p + dF_p$. Here $F_p = f_p^* f_p$.

Then:

$$U = \sum_p F_p p^2/2m \quad \text{where } p=6.28 n/L \quad \text{and } dU = \sum_p p dF_p p^2/2m$$

$$TdS = k \{ - \sum_p dF_p \ln(F_p) - \sum_p T dF_p \}$$

This essentially leads to $F_p = \exp(-p^2/2mT)$ or $f_p = \exp(-p^2/4mT)$.

Taking the Fourier transform yields:

$$W(x) = \sum_{n=1,2,3,\dots} \exp(-pn^2 \pi^2 / 2mT) \sin(pn x) \quad \text{where } pn = 6.28 n/L \quad ((4.5))$$

If pn were continuous, this would yield a Gaussian $W(x) = \exp(-ax^2)$, but this would not satisfy the boundary conditions at $x=0$ and $x=L$. (Note, the Gaussian solution matches the ground state of a harmonic oscillator.)

Comparison with Existing Theories

In (1) and (2), new Schrodinger type equations in x space are developed using the idea that $dU = TdS$ from thermodynamics. The same idea has been used in the section above. In (1), $S = -k \ln(\text{density})$, where $\text{density} = W(x)W(x)$. In (2), this has been criticized and an entropy density of $S = -k d(x) \ln[d(x)]$ where $d(x)$ is density applied, i.e. Shannon's entropy has been used. The single particle equation for (1) is given by:

$$\hbar d/d W(x,t) = (-\hbar^2/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x)W(x) + kT \ln[W(x)W(x)] W(x) \quad ((5))$$

If $W(x,t) = \exp(iEt)W(x)$ for a resonance, then one obtains a time-independent type of Schrodinger equation.

For (2) it is:

$$\hbar d/d W(x,t) = (-\hbar^2/2m) d/dx d/dx W(x) + V(x)W(x) - kT \ln[B] W(x) \quad ((6))$$

Where $\ln[B]$ is assumed to be $-W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x))$. Here B is the number of states.

Let us consider the solution ((4.5)) and the two equations ((5)) and ((6)). To simplify, assume ((4.5)) is applied to a large box with L approaching infinity. Then $W(x) = C \exp(-ax^2)$. Equation ((5)) yields (with $\hbar=1$):

$$(1/2m) (2a - 4a^2 x^2) - T (-2ax^2) = E \quad \text{Thus, one can choose } T \text{ proportional to } E \text{ so that the } x^2 \text{ terms cancel and the solution ((4.5)) satisfies ((5)).}$$

For ((6)):

$$(1/2m) (2a - 4a^2 x^2) - T C \exp(-2ax^2) (-2ax^2) = E \quad \text{This leads to a } T \text{ which is not constant}$$

In evaluating ((6)) we have used $-d(x) \ln[d(x)]$ for the entropy which is listed in the paper as equation 20. Now, in (2), the entropy term is written as $-kT \ln[B] W(x)$, but it is not clear what B

is as a function of x . It is formally defined in the paper as the number of states in a microcanonical distribution. Perhaps, we have misinterpreted the evaluation of $-\ln(B)$ here.

Nevertheless, using a momentum approach together with $dU=TdS$ does seem to produce results very similar to those of the new Schrodinger type equations in x space. The calculation here, however, has been done in momentum space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, new temperature dependent Schrodinger equations with an extra potential term based on T and the wavefunction itself seem to be different from models used in the past. In this note, we suggest that one can use $dU=TdS$ and calculate $S=-k \sum p^2 f_p \ln(f_p)$ and then vary the f_p 's to obtain dS (and also dU). This seems to lead to results consistent with the new spatial temperature dependent equations appearing in the literature.

References

1. Wu, Xiang-Yao, Zhang, Bai-Jun, et al, Finite Temperature Schrodinger Equation (2011) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1005.2751.pdf>
2. Li, Heling, Yang, Bin and Xiong, Ying The New Finite Temperature Schrodinger Equation <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1211.3195.pdf>